

1 New early Miocene material of *Iberictis*, the oldest member of the wolverine lineage
2 (Carnivora, Mustelidae, Guloninae)

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26

27 **Abstract**

28 We describe new dental remains of the genus *Iberictis* (Carnivora: Mustelidae)
29 from the late early Miocene of the Iberian Peninsula. The new fossils of *Iberictis*
30 *azanzae* from Artesilla (16.5–16.3 Ma, MN4; Calatayud-Teruel Basin, Zaragoza, Spain)
31 add important morphological information about this species. Material from another
32 species, *Iberictis buloti*, is described from els Casots (16.5–16.3 Ma, MN4; Vallès-
33 Penedès Basin, Barcelona, Spain). This material constitutes the most complete sample
34 of *Iberictis* and the first record of *I. buloti* in the Iberian Peninsula. Our analyses
35 confirm the taxonomic validity of both species, and confirms the more plesiomorphic
36 status of *I. buloti* compared to *I. azanzae*. Re-examination of large mustelid Miocene
37 genera (*Dehmictis*, *Ekorus*, *Eomellivora*, *Hoplictis*, *Iberictis*, *Ischyriactis*, and
38 *Plesiogulo*) and their inclusion for the first time in a cladistic analysis indicate that
39 *Iberictis* is the sister taxon of *Plesiogulo*, and that these genera constitute the sister
40 group of the extant wolverine (*Gulo gulo*). Our analysis thus confirms a close
41 relationship between the early Miocene *Iberictis*, the late Miocene *Plesiogulo*, and the
42 Plio-Pleistocene *Gulo*. *Iberictis* is the oldest member of Gulonini, the total clade of
43 wolverines, thereby tracking the fossil record of this clade back to the early Miocene.
44 We further propose a new systematic arrangement for the aforementioned large
45 Miocene mustelids into the subfamilies Guloninae, Mellivorinae, and Mustelinae.

46

47 **Introduction**

48 The subfamily Guloninae is currently composed of generalist and hypercarnivorous
49 mustelids, distributed over much of North America and Eurasia, and with a single genus
50 in Central and South America. The extant members of this clade are included in three

51 main groups: (1) a heterogeneous group of small- to medium-sized taxa, comprised of
52 the fisher (*Pekania* Gray, 1865) and martens (*Martes* Pinel, 1792, and *Charronia* Gray,
53 1865); (2) the medium-sized Latin American tayra (*Eira* Smith, 1842); and (3) the
54 large-sized wolverine (*Gulo* Pallas, 1780). This subfamily was formerly referred to as
55 the Martinae but Guloninae has priority (Sato et al. 2009; Samuels and Cavin 2013).
56 Gulonines have a conservative morphology that hinders morphology-based studies of
57 their phylogenetic relationships (Anderson 1970; Samuels and Cavin 2013).

58 This study focuses on the lineage of the wolverine, the largest terrestrial extant
59 mustelid and one of the most iconic members of this family. It is restricted to mature
60 conifer forests in the taiga and the treeless tundra from the North Holarctic region
61 (Larivière and Jennings 2009). The origin of the wolverine lineage remains obscure, but
62 according to recent molecular analyses the lineage of *Gulo* diverged from *Martes* 7.6–
63 5.5 Ma (Li et al. 2014; Malyarchuk et al. 2015). A sister group relationship between
64 *Gulo* and *Martes* is supported by Samuels et al. (2018) using evidence of a new species
65 of *Gulo* from the early Pliocene (4.9–4.5 Ma) of Tennessee. However, this time interval
66 also coincides with the expansion of the wolverine-like extinct mustelid *Plesiogulo*
67 Zdansky, 1924, characterized by a large to giant body size. *Plesiogulo* has been found in
68 Eurasia, North America, and Africa (e.g., Zdansky 1924; Viret 1939; Teilhard 1945;
69 Kurtén 1970; Hendey 1978; Harrison 1981; Alcalá et al. 1994; Sotnikova 1995; Haile-
70 Selassie et al. 2004; Morales et al. 2005, 2016; Montoya et al. 2011), spanning from the
71 late Miocene (MN10) to the early Pliocene (MN14). Viret (1939), Kurtén (1970), and
72 Kurtén and Anderson (1980) supported a direct relationship between *Plesiogulo* and
73 *Gulo*, based on general dental similarities, whereas other authors considered that
74 *Plesiogulo* constitutes a distinct phylogenetic lineage without living descendants
75 (Zdansky 1924; Hendey 1978; Harrison 1981; Xiaofeng and Haipo 1987; Alcalá et al.

76 1994; Sotnikova 1995; Montoya et al. 2011). Samuels et al. (2018) also considered
77 *Plesiogulo* to be convergent with *Gulo*. However, the cladistic analysis of Valenciano et
78 al. (2017) on some living and extinct gulonines and mellivorines grouped *Plesiogulo*
79 and *Gulo* as the sister taxon to the beech marten, *Martes foina* (Erxleben, 1777) and the
80 fisher, *Pekania pennanti* (Erxleben, 1777).

81 *Iberictis* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992, is a medium-size mustelid known from
82 scarce remains from the early Miocene (MN4) of Europe. This genus comprises two
83 species: *Iberictis azanzae* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992, from Artesilla (MN4, Spain)
84 and *Iberictis buloti* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992, from Pellicahus (MN4, France).
85 According to Ginsburg and Morales (1992), *Iberictis* shows strong affinities with
86 *Plesiogulo*, despite of the significant temporal gap between them. Here, we report new
87 material of *I. azanzae* from the early Miocene (MN4) of Artesilla (Calatayud-Teruel
88 Basin, Zaragoza, Spain) and abundant new material of *I. buloti* from the early Miocene
89 (MN4) site of els Casots (Subirats, Catalonia, Spain). These fossils provide novel
90 information for *Iberictis* and shed new light on the phylogenetic relationships of large
91 Miocene mustelids belonging to the wolverine lineage. The aims of this paper are
92 threefold: (1) to describe the remains of *Iberictis* from Artesilla and els Casots, while
93 justifying their taxonomic ascription to species rank; (2) to perform a cladistic analysis
94 in order to test the hypothesis that *Iberictis* is related to *Plesiogulo* and/or *Gulo*; and (3)
95 to evaluate the relationships of this wolverine group with most of the medium- to large-
96 sized Miocene mustelids, in order to further clarify their evolutionary history.

97

98 **Age and geological background of els Casots**

99 The presence of fossil vertebrate remains in the municipality of Subirats (Catalonia,
100 Spain) has been known for many decades, but the site of els Casots was not discovered

101 until 1989. Subsequently excavated until 1994, els Casots has yielded abundant micro-
102 and macrovertebrate remains, including fishes, amphibians, reptiles, birds, and
103 mammals (Moyà-Solà and Rius Font 1993; Agustí and Llenas 1993; Casanovas-Vilar et
104 al. 2011a). However, except for crocodylians (Díaz Aráez et al. 2016), some rodent
105 species (Aldana Carrasco 1991, 1992; Ginestí 2008; Jovells-Vaqué et al. 2017), and
106 various artiodactyl groups (Pickford and Moyà-Solà 1994, 1995; Duranthon et al. 1995;
107 van der Made 1997; Orliac 2006; Alba et al. 2014), most of the fauna (carnivorans
108 included) remains unpublished.

109 Els Casots is located in the Vallès-Penedès Basin (Fig. 1), an elongated
110 semigraben delimited by the Catalan Coastal Ranges (Littoral and Prelittoral) in NE
111 Iberian Peninsula (Cabrera et al. 2004; de Gibert and Casanovas-Vilar 2011). This basin
112 has delivered a rich fossil vertebrate record ranging from the late Ramblian (MN3) to
113 the middle Turolian (MN12), i.e., ca. 20–7 Ma (Casanovas-Vilar et al. 2011b, 2016).
114 Els Casots represents an ancient lacustrine system overlying Mesozoic deposits and
115 situated within the early Miocene Detritic-Carbonated Unit of Subirats, which
116 corresponds to the Lower Continental Complexes of the Vallès-Penedès Basin (Moyà-
117 Solà and Rius Font 1993; de Gibert and Casanovas-Vilar 2011; Casanovas-Vilar et al.
118 2011a,c). Mostly on the basis of small mammal biostratigraphy, the site is correlated to
119 MN4 (early Aragonian, early Miocene) and, in particular, to local zone C of the
120 Calatayud-Daroca Basin, with an estimated age of 16.5–16.3 Ma (Casanovas-Vilar et al.
121 2011a, b, c, 2016; Jovells-Vaqué et al. 2017).

122

123 **Material and Methods**

124 **Nomenclature and Measurements**

125 Dental nomenclature follows Ginsburg (1999) and Smith and Dodson (2003).
126 Measurements were taken using a Mitutoyo Absolute digital caliper to the nearest 0.1
127 mm.

128

129 **Abbreviations**

130 **Institutional Abbreviations** **AMNH**: American Museum of Natural History, New
131 York, USA; **BSPG**: Bayerische Staatssammlung für Paläontologie und Geologie,
132 Munich, Germany; **FCPT**: Fundación Conjunto Paleontológico de Teruel-Dinópolis,
133 Museo Aragonés de Paleontología, Teruel, Spain; **FSL**: Université Claude Bernard
134 Lyon 1; **ICP**: Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont, Universitat Autònoma
135 de Barcelona, Spain; **IPS**: collections from the ICP (formerly 'Institut de Paleontologia
136 de Sabadell'); **MGUV**: Museu de Geologia de la Universitat de València, Burjassot,
137 Spain; **MNCN**: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales Madrid, Spain; **MNHN**:
138 Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France; **MPZ**: collection of the former
139 Museo Paleontológico de la Universidad de Zaragoza, currently housed at the Museo de
140 Ciencias Naturales Universidad de Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain; **NHMW**:
141 Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Vienna, Austria; **NMB**: Naturhistorisches Museum
142 Basel, Switzerland; **NRM**: Naturhistoriska riksmuseet, Stockholm, Sweden; **PMU**:
143 Palaeontological Museum, University of Uppsala, Uppsala, Sweden; **SAM**: Iziko
144 Museums of South Africa, Cape Town, South Africa; **SMNS**: Staatliches Museum für
145 Naturkunde, Stuttgart, Germany; **USNM**: Smithsonian National Museum of Natural
146 History, Washington, D.C., USA.

147

148 **Studied Material**

149 The fossil remains of *I. azanzae* from Artesilla are housed at the MPZ. The newly

150 described sample includes: MPZ-2018/42, left P4 protocone; MPZ-2018/43, right
151 fragment of M1 including the styler area, the paracone and the metacone; MPZ-
152 2018/39, left c with the tip broken; MPZ-2018/40, crown of a left c; MPZ-2018/41,
153 incomplete left p4. The fossil remains of *Iberictis* from els Casots are housed at the ICP.
154 The studied sample includes: IPS10076, right fragment of cranium with I3, C, P2–M1;
155 IPS10077, left maxillary fragment with P4–M1; IPS10083, right maxillary fragment of
156 skull with P2–P4; IPS24701, cranium fragmented in two pieces, the left one with the
157 rostral part of the zygomatic arch, the ventral orbital area, and part of the maxillary bone
158 (comprising the distal portion of the P3, the complete P4, and the broken M1, with the
159 lingual platform and protocone), and the right fragment with P2 and P3 broken at the
160 base of the root (the distal area of the P3 is preserved), the complete P4 and an almost
161 complete M1 (with a missing both metacone and distal part of the tooth); IPS100599,
162 left maxillary fragment with a complete P3 and the mesial part of the P4; IPS36425,
163 isolated teeth of a single individual, comprising the left P3, P4 with a small portion of
164 the maxillary bone, and an M1 fragment with the lingual platform and protocone;
165 IPS10085, right C; IPS10086, left C; IPS24159, right C; IPS85598, right P4; IPS10072,
166 left M1; IPS105255, left M1 fragment comprising the lingual platform and protocone;
167 IPS24107, left mandibular fragment with isolated p4, fragmentary m1, and complete
168 m2; IPS24700, mandible with left p3–p4 and right c and p2–m1; IPS85595, right
169 mandibular fragment with fragmentary p4–m1; IPS10084, right mandibular fragment
170 with p2–m1; IPS10069, left mandibular fragment with p4–m1; IPS24686, fragmentary
171 mandible with right p4–m1 and left p4 (partial) and m1; IPS10079, right hemimandible
172 with p3–m1; IPS10080, left hemimandible with p2–p4; IPS10066, left hemimandible
173 with c, p2–m2; IPS10067, right hemimandible with c and p2–m1; IPS10068, right
174 hemimandible with c and p2–m1; IPS10070, left p3, and a left mandibular ramus

175 fragment with p4 broken at the level of the roots and partial m1 that only preserves part
176 of the trigonid; IPS105256, left p4; IPS10088, right m2.

177 The comparative material of large Miocene mustelids consists of the following
178 taxa: *Ekorus ekakeran* Werdelin, 2003 (cast) from Lothagam, Kenya, from the research
179 collection of L. Werdelin housed at NRM; *Eomellivora piveteaui* Ozansoy, 1965, from
180 Cerro de los Batallones, Spain (Valenciano et al. 2015), housed at MNCN; *Hoplictis*
181 *noueli* (Mayet, 1908) from Artenay, France, housed at MNHN and NMB; the classic
182 material of *Iberictis* described by Ginsburg and Morales (1992), including the type
183 material of *I. azanzae* from Artesilla, Spain, housed at MPZ, and that of *I. buloti* from
184 Pellecahus, France, housed at MNHN; *Ischyriictis mustelinus* (Viret, 1933), from Can
185 Mata 1, els Hostalets de Pierola, Spain, housed at ICP (Villalta Comella and Crusafont
186 Pairó 1943; Crusafont and Truyols 1954; Petter 1963); *Ischyriictis zibethoides*
187 (Blainville, 1842) from Sansan, France, housed at MNHN; *Plesiogulo crassa* Teilhard,
188 1945, from Localities 30, 108 and 111 from China (Kurtén 1970), housed at PMU;
189 *Plesiogulo monspessulanus* Viret, 1939, from Montpellier, France, housed at FSL, also
190 the specimens from Venta del Moro and Las Casiones, Spain, housed at MGUV and
191 FCPT respectively, and the specimens from Langebaanweg, South Africa, housed at
192 SAM; *Plesiogulo lindsayi* Harrison, 1981, from Wikieup, Old Cabin Quarry, and
193 Redington Quarry in Arizona, USA, housed at AMNH; *Plesiogulo marshalli* (Martin,
194 1928) from Edson Quarry in Kansas, USA, Optima in Oklahoma, USA, Coffee Ranch
195 in Texas, USA, Modesto reservoir in California, USA, San Juan Quarry in New
196 Mexico, USA, and Boney Valley in Florida, USA housed at AMNH; and *Lartetictis*
197 *dubia* (Blainville, 1842) from Sansan, France, housed at MNHN. We further inspected
198 photographs of *Dehmictis vorax* (Dehm, 1950) from Wintershof-West, Germany,
199 housed at BSPG; *Ischyriictis mustelinus* from La Grive-Saint-Alban, France, housed at

200 FSL, and Erkertshofen 2, Germany (Viret 1933; Roth 1989), housed at FSL and SMNS;
201 *Plesiogulo* sp. from Paşalar, Turkey (Schmidt-Kittler 1976), housed at BSPG; and
202 *Paralutra jaegeri* (Frass, 1862) from Ravensburg and Steinheim, Germany, housed at
203 SMNS. *Gulo schlosseri* Kormos, 1914, was also studied based on a cast of the holotype
204 from Püspökfürdo, Hungary, housed at NHMW and the publications by Kormos (1914)
205 and Bonifay (1971). The extant comparative sample included the mustelids *Gulo gulo*
206 Linnaeus, 1758, *Mellivora capensis* (Schreber 1776), and *Mustela putorius* Linnaeus,
207 1758, the mephitid *Mephitis mephitis* (Schreber, 1776), and the procyonid *Bassariscus*
208 *astutus* (Lichtenstein, 1830), housed at AMNH, MNCN, NRM, and USNM.

209

210 **Cladistics Analysis**

211 In order to better understand the phylogenetic relationships of *Iberictis* in relation to
212 medium to large Miocene mustelids—*Dehmictis* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992, *Ekorus*
213 Werdelin, 2003, *Eomellivora* Zdansky, 1924, *Hoplictis* Ginsburg, 1961, *Ischyriictis*
214 Helbing, 1930, and *Plesiogulo*—as well as relative to selected extant mustelids, we
215 performed a cladistic analysis including 18 taxa—*Iberictis buloti* is represented as two
216 different operational taxonomic units (OTU), one for the previously-known remains of
217 this taxon, and the other for the newly-described specimens from els Casots—and 76
218 equally-weighted and unordered dental characters (Appendix 1), based on Wolsan
219 (1993), Bryant et al. (1993), Wesley-Hunt and Werdelin (2005), and Valenciano et al.
220 (2015, 2016a, 2017). The musteloids *Mephitis mephitis* and *Bassariscus astutus* were
221 included as outgroups. The data matrix was compiled in Mesquite 3.01 for Mac.
222 Cladistics analysis was performed with PAUP* 4.0b10 (Swofford 2002), using the
223 ‘branch and bound’ search command. Clade robusticity was assessed by means of
224 bootstrap with 1,000 replicates and Bremer support indices. The used character/taxon

225 matrix and character state definitions are reported in the Appendices 1–3. The
226 distribution of character states for internal nodes was analyzed with Mesquite 3.01 and
227 PAUP* 4.0b10.
228 The dataset generated during and/or analyzed during the current study is available from
229 the corresponding author on reasonable request.

230 **Systematic Paleontology**

231

232 Order **CARNIVORA** Bowdich, 1821

233 Suborder **CANIFORMIA** Kretzoi, 1943

234 Family **MUSTELIDAE** Fischer, 1817

235 Subfamily **GULONINAE** Gray, 1825

236

237 Genus ***IBERICTIS*** Ginsburg and Morales, 1992

238

239 *Original diagnosis:* (Reproduced from Ginsburg and Morales 1992: pp. 116; our
240 translation from the French original). “Mustelid of large size, P4–M1 close to those of
241 *Plesiogulo* with a prominent P4 with protocone strong and very distinct, isolated from
242 the mesial border of the paracone by a heavy concavity; M1 very elongated
243 buccolingually with a short buccal wall and an enlarged lingual platform extended
244 backward as in *Plesiogulo* and *Trochictis*. *Ischyriictis*-like lower teeth with a long m1
245 with a prominent entoconid; m2 longer than in *Ischyriictis*.”

246 *Emended diagnosis:* Medium-sized gulonine mustelid with wrinkled enamel and a
247 robust P4 that displays a concavity between parastyle and protocone; P4 with a high and
248 enlarged protocone, and a variably developed lingual cingulum that thickens distally to
249 protocone; M1 with distolingual enlargement of lingual platform (which possesses a

250 concavity on its middle portion) and without hypocone; p4 with lingual bulge and
251 entirely surrounded by stout cingulid with thickened mesial and distal cristids; m1 with
252 protoconid higher than paraconid, pronounced metaconid (not entoconid as in original
253 diagnosis), and beveled lingual wall of hypoconid; m2 plesiomorphic, with very
254 pronounced metaconid and hypoconid, and with trigonid and talonid roots incompletely
255 fused (resulting in a marked notch in the single m2 alveolus).

256 *Differential diagnosis:* *Iberictis* differs from the other gulonines *Plesiogulo*, *Gulo*,
257 *Ischyriictis* in having a smaller size, and more robust and higher P4 protocone that trends
258 to form a lingual shelf. From *Plesiogulo* and *Gulo* in the presence of a P4 protocone
259 mesially located, a higher and more massive M1 metacone, and in the presence of both
260 metaconule and postprotocrista. It differs from *Plesiogulo* in the elongated P2;
261 relatively higher and slender lower premolars; a less developed m1 hypoconulid; and a
262 more primitive m2 with hypoconid. It differs from *Gulo* in longer and slender
263 premolars; shorter P4; longer M1 lingual platform with a small concavity on the middle
264 part of the lingual platform; slender m1 trigonid, presence of m1 metaconid and longer
265 talonid with more massive hypoconid; and less reduced m2. Compared to *Ischyriictis*
266 and *Dehmictis* it differs in more developed M1 lingual platform. It differs from
267 *Ischyriictis* in the presence of lingual concavity on M1 lingual platform; in more massive
268 cingula and cristis in lower premolars, without distal accessory cuspids; m1 with more
269 developed metaconid and hypoconid, and relatively shorter talonid. It differs from
270 *Dehmictis* in higher and robust P4 protocone that trends to form lingual shelf and
271 shorter and less basined m1 talonid; and in bigger size. It differs from the basal
272 mellivorine *Hoplictis* in the shorter P4; larger M1 with both a more developed metacone
273 and lingual platform; in absence of accessory cuspids in premolars; in more developed
274 m1 metaconid and in longer m1 talonid. Besides, it differs from the primitive lutrines

275 *Paralutra* Roman and Viret, 1934, *Lartetictis* Ginsburg and Morales, 1996, and
276 *Siamogale* Ginsburg et al., 1983, in relatively longer P4 with lesser developed P4
277 lingual shelf and without hypocone; in M1 more mesiodistally constricted below
278 paracone-metacone, with lesser mesiodistal expansion of lingual platform and absence
279 of hypocone; and in more massive and beveled m1 hypoconid. It differs from *Paralutra*
280 in wider M1 with less basined m1 talonid. It differs from *Lartetictis* and *Siamogale* in
281 having smaller size, in shorter talon and talonid in M1 and m1, higher m1 crown, lesser
282 m1 metaconid, and narrower m2. It differs from *Siamogale* in less bunodont and slender
283 lower premolars; much smaller m1 metaconid and in smaller talonid with much
284 slenderer and shorter m1 entocristid.

285

286 *Type species: Iberictis azanzae* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992.

287 *Other included species: Iberictis buloti* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992.

288

289 ***Iberictis azanzae*** Ginsburg and Morales, 1992

290 (Figs. 2, 6A)

291 *Holotype:* MPZ-16522, left maxillary fragment with P4 and partial M1 with the
292 lingual platform and protocone.

293 *Type locality:* Artesilla (Calatayud-Teruel Basin, Zaragoza, Spain).

294 *Age:* Early Miocene (MN4).

295 *Remarks:* In addition to the material described by Ginsburg and Morales (1992)
296 from Artesilla, we describe new material from this locality obtained during the screen-
297 washing of sediments for micromammal sampling. The P4 protocone MPZ-2018/42
298 (Fig. 2A) is very similar to that of the holotype, except for a larger wear facet in the
299 protocone. MPZ-2018/43 is a right buccal fragment of M1 (Fig. 2B)—missing in the

300 holotype and previously unknown for the species. It possesses an enlarged styler area
301 with a stout cingulum. Both the paracone and the metacone have a wear facet. The
302 paracone is the highest cusp and has a distal crista connecting with the metacone, which
303 is located below the paracone. The presence of a metaconule cannot be ascertained
304 because the tooth is broken in this area. The two canines have wrinkled enamel, are oval
305 in cross-section, and markedly curved distally, and have a strong lingual cristid in
306 contact with a stout cingulid (Fig. 2C–D). The left p4 MPZ-2018/41 (Fig. 2E) lacks its
307 mesial portion. It is unicuspid and shows a strong wear facet on the tip of the cuspid. It
308 possesses thick mesial and distal cristids, and a strong cingulid surrounding the whole
309 crown, with an evident basal lingual bulge.

310

311 *Iberictis buloti* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992

312 (Figs. 3, 4, 6B-E, 10A-C,F)

313 *Holotype*: MNHN LRM 1044, right hemimandible with p3–m1 with worn
314 dentition.

315 *Type locality*: Pellecahus (France)

316 *Other localities*: els Casots (Subirats, Vallès-Penedès Basin, Catalonia, Spain).

317 *Age*: Early Miocene (MN4).

318 *Original diagnosis*: (Reproduced from Ginsburg and Morales 1992: 116; our
319 translation from the French original). “*Iberictis* smaller than *I. azanzae*. P4 protocone
320 less distinct; M1 lingual platform less prominent.”

321 *Emended diagnosis*: *Iberictis* species smaller than *I. azanzae*; P4 protocone not
322 individualized, with lingual cingulum markedly thickened distal to protocone; p2–p4
323 stout and without accessory cuspids, surrounded by a stout cingulid with thickened
324 mesial and distal cristids; m2 hypoconid very pronounced.

325 *Differential diagnosis:* It differs from *I. azanzae* in less distinct P4 protocone;
326 relatively shorter P4; presence of postprotocrista in M1; lesser distolingual enlargement
327 of M1; and more developed m2 hypoconid.

328

329 **Description of the material from els Casots**

330

331 **Maxilla and upper dentition** The preserved maxillary specimens from els Casots
332 (IPS85598, IPS10076, IPS24701, IPS100599, IPS36425, IPS10077, and IPS10083) are
333 quite fragmentary (Fig. 3), but based on IPS10076, the muzzle appears to have been
334 short, with the orbital shape and height of the nasal aperture resembling those of
335 martens and fishers (*Martes* and *Pekania*). The infraorbital foramen is not preserved.
336 The dentition possesses wrinkled enamel, which is most conspicuous in the C, the P4,
337 M1, and the lower dentition. The preserved upper dentition includes the I1–I3, the C,
338 and the P2–M1 row (Table 1). The I1 and I2 are quite damaged, but the I3 is not
339 enlarged compared to the other incisors (Fig. 3A). The C is oval in cross-section,
340 displays radial crenulations from the tip to the base of the crown, and has a strong
341 cingulum (Fig. 3B, C). The presence or absence of P1 cannot be assessed based on the
342 available material. The P2–P4 exhibit a strong cingulum that surrounds the whole
343 crown. The P2 is elongated, oval in occlusal view, and unicuspid. The P3 is
344 subrectangular in occlusal view, elongated, and unicuspid, with a buccodistal bulge and
345 a pronounced concavity at the base of its buccal wall (Fig. 3D2). The P4 has a robust
346 cingular parastyle located on the mesial cingulum. Mesially, there is an inflection
347 between the protocone and parastyle, and the paracone and parastyle are connected by a
348 thick crista. The protocone is stout, very high, conical, and projected mesiolingually, but
349 aligned with the parastyle (Fig. 3D, E-G, I). There is a thick cingulum surrounding the

350 whole crown, with a lingual shelf that runs from the base of the protocone to beneath
351 that of the paracone. On this lingual shelf, next to the protocone, there is a concavity,
352 more evident in IPS10083, IPS24701, and IPS36425 (Fig. 3D, F2, I). The buccal wall
353 between the paracone and metastyle is concave. The M1 is robust and subequal in size
354 to the P4. The styler area is large and has a swollen cingulum. The paracone is larger
355 than the metacone, which is somewhat more lingually situated. There is a constriction in
356 the crown mid-length. Mesially the M1 has a small crest-shaped paraconule in contact
357 with the protocone. On the distal corner of the crown there is also a small metaconule
358 aligned with the paraconule, being more conspicuous in IPS10072, IPS36425, and
359 IPS105255 (Fig. 3J, K, L). The protocone is crest-like and located on the lingual corner.
360 It has a postprotocrista, more patent in IPS24701, IPS10072, IPS36425, IPS105255, and
361 IPS10077 (Fig. 3E, J, K, L, M). The M1 shows an additional slender buccolingual crista
362 connecting the paracone with the protocone. It has a mesiodistally enlarged lingual
363 platform with a small concavity on the middle, and which is even more pronounced in
364 the distolingual area (being particularly evident in IPS10077 and IPS105255; Fig. 3J,
365 M).

366

367 **Mandible and lower dentition** The mandibular corpus is high, with a very stout ventral
368 edge. There is a single rounded mental foramen under the p2 and p3 (Fig. 4). The ramus
369 is high. The postcanine tooth row is straight. The c is oval in cross-section and
370 markedly curved distally (Fig. 4A, Table 2). There is a strong lingual cristid in contact
371 with a stout cingulid. The p1 is absent (Fig. 4A3, E2). The p2–p4 have a single cuspid,
372 thick mesial and distal cristids, and a strong cingulid surrounding the whole crown (Fig.
373 4). The p2 is slender and somewhat shorter compared to the p3, which slightly widens
374 distally. The p4 has a noticeable basal lingual bulge (Fig. 4C3, D3, G3). The m1 is

375 elongated. The protoconid is higher than the paraconid. The metaconid is robust. The
376 hypoconid is low, pyramidal, stout, buccally located, and occupies an important area of
377 the talonid. The lingual wall of the talonid is beveled, without entoconid, with a
378 peripheral entocristid connecting the metaconid to the hypoconid (Fig. 4A3, B3). There
379 is no hypoconulid. The alveolus of the m2 is oval and somewhat elongated. It is single-
380 rooted, with a remarkable notch in the alveolus, indicating the somewhat incomplete
381 fusion of the trigonid and talonid roots—unlike living mustelids, which have a reduced
382 single root with no traces of fusion (Fig. 4A3). The m2 is oval, with well distinct
383 cuspids (paraconid, protoconid, metaconid, and hypoconid; Fig. 4H, I). The trigonid is
384 wider than the talonid. The paraconid is crest-shaped, and the protoconid, metaconid,
385 and hypoconid are pyramidal. The protoconid and metaconid are the highest cuspids,
386 particularly the protoconid. The internal cristids of these cuspids are thickened and
387 connected in the middle of the tooth, producing a clear separation between the basins of
388 the trigonid and the talonid. The hypoconid is centrally located and occupies the whole
389 talonid, being most developed in IPS24107 and IPS10088. A continuous and strong
390 cingulid is present.

391

392 **Cladistic results**

393 Our cladistic analysis recovered three equally most-parsimonious trees, with a tree
394 length of 187 steps, a consistency index (CI) of 0.4545, a rescaled consistency index
395 (RC) of 0.2941, and a retention index (RI) of 0.6471. The apomorphies for each node
396 are reported in Table 3. Our analysis only fails to resolve the relationships among some
397 species of *Plesiogulo*. The strict consensus tree (Fig. 5) recovers two major clades: the
398 Guloninae, composed of the monophyletic clade of *Iberictis*, *Plesiogulo*, *Gulo*, and
399 *Dehmictis*+*Ischyriictis*; and a clade composed of the paraphyletic Mellivorinae—which

400 include the living *Mellivora capensis* and the extinct mellivorines *Eomellivora*
401 *piveteaui*, *Ekorus ekakeran*, and *Hoplictis noueli*—as well as the extant musteline
402 *Mustela putorius*. Among the Guloninae, two different tribes (Gulonini and Ischyriictini)
403 may be recognized: (1) the Gulonini, composed of *Iberictis* spp. (*I. buloti* and *I.*
404 *azanzae*), *Plesiogulo* spp., and *Gulo* spp.; and (2) the Ischyriictini, including the genera
405 *Dehmictis* and *Ischyriictis*. The monophyly of both the Gulonini and of the genera
406 *Iberictis*, *Plesiogulo* and *Gulo* are supported by bootstrap results and Bremer indices
407 (Fig. 5: Nodes B, D, F, and H). Our cladistic analysis therefore supports an *Iberictis*
408 clade sister of *Plesiogulo*, with these clades jointly constituting the sister clade of the
409 extant *Gulo*. The remains of *Iberictis* from els Casots are nested with those of *I. buloti*
410 from the type locality (Pellecahus), in agreement with their attribution to the same
411 species.

412 The recovery of a mellivorine clade partially agrees with the phylogenetic
413 relationship supported by Valenciano et al. (2015, 2017), according to which
414 *Eomellivora piveteaui* and *Ekorus ekakeran* would be allied with the living honey
415 badger (*Mellivora capensis*). The early Miocene *Hoplictis noueli* is recovered as a stem
416 mellivorine. Both the *Ekorus+Mellivora* and *Eomellivora+(Ekorus+Mellivora)* clades
417 are well supported (Fig. 5). The position of *Mustela putorius* in the recovered strict
418 consensus is controversial (see the Discussion for more details).

419

420 **Discussion**

421 **Taxonomic Attribution**

422 *Iberictis* was considered to be closely related to *Plesiogulo* by Ginsburg and Morales
423 (1992). These authors erected two species of this genus, both from the early Miocene

424 (MN4) of Europe, based on the then available scarce material: the type species, *I.*
425 *azanzae*, from Artesilla (Zaragoza, Spain; Fig. 6A); and *I. buloti* from Pellecahus
426 (France; Fig. 6B, E1–E3). Since their description, no further fossil remains of *Iberictis*
427 have been described. The new sample of *I. azanzae* from Artesilla adds very important
428 information about the M1 morphology, complementing the information provided by the
429 holotype (Fig. 6A) and corroborating a close relationship between *I. azanzae* and *I.*
430 *buloti*.

431 The new fossils described here from the MN4 of els Casots are assigned to
432 *Iberictis* because they display the diagnostic features of this genus (e.g., lingual
433 platform of the M1 distolingually enlarged, and unicuspid p4 with lingual bulge as well
434 as thickened mesial and distal cristids; see our emended diagnosis above for further
435 details). The sample from els Casots is considerably larger than that previously known
436 for this genus (Tables 1 and 2), being composed of the remains from at least seven
437 individuals (based on right hemimandibles), and thus it allows us to expand greatly the
438 knowledge about this genus. The ranges of variation observed within the described
439 sample agree with those ascertained for extant large mustelids such as *Mellivora*
440 *capensis* and *Gulo gulo* (Figs. 3, 4, 7, and 8). The P4s from els Casots show a variable
441 development of the lingual shelf that runs from the base of the protocone to beneath that
442 of the paracone as well as of the concavity situated on this lingual shelf. In particular,
443 specimens with a larger lingual shelf have a larger concavity as well (e.g., IPS10083
444 and IPS36425; Fig. 3D, I). Another variable feature is the differential degree of
445 development of the M1 metaconule and postprotocrista, which are more remarkable in
446 IPS10072, IPS36425, and IPS105255 (Fig. 3J, K, L). Two (out of the seven available)
447 M1s are completely preserved (IPS10077 and IPS10072; Fig. 6C, D), and display some
448 morphological differences relative to one another. In particular, IPS10077 (Fig. 6C)

449 displays a more symmetrical lingual platform than IPS10072 (Fig. 6D), whose platform
450 is larger distolingually. Another example of variability is the very reduced bulge
451 (IPS10067), or even the small convexity (IPS10069), present on the distal cristid of the
452 p4, which reflects the reduction of the distal accessory cuspid on this tooth (Fig. 3A2,
453 B2). The remains of *Iberictis* from els Casots most closely resemble those of *I. buloti*
454 from Pellecahus, including a similar size and an almost identical morphology of the
455 premolars as compared with the type species—with the exception of the more
456 pronounced buccal concavity in the P3 and the more primitive morphology of the p4,
457 which retains a vestigial distal accessory cuspid in the els Casots sample. The
458 specimens from els Casots display some minor differences in dental proportions as
459 compared to those of *I. buloti* from Pellecahus for some tooth loci (e.g., the P3), but
460 nevertheless these differences can be easily accommodated within the variability range of
461 a single species (Figs. 7 and 8), particularly taking into account the small sample size
462 previously available for *I. buloti* from the type locality. Given the lack of relevant
463 morphological differences between these two samples, we formally assign the sample
464 from els Casots to *I. buloti*. In contrast, the sample from els Casots differs from *I.*
465 *azanzae* in the lack of the derived traits characteristic of the latter: enlarged cutting edge
466 of the P4, better individualized P4 protocone, greater distolingual enlargement of the
467 M1, absence of postprotocrista in M1, and the lesser development of cuspids in m2.
468 Therefore the new material from els Casots and Artesilla described here fills an
469 important gap in the knowledge of this mustelid genus *Iberictis* and confirms the
470 distinctiveness of the two originally described species. The presence of both species in
471 the Iberian Peninsula during the early Miocene might be attributable to
472 paleogeographical factors. Both localities are correlated to MN4, and in particular to
473 local zone C of the Calatayud-Daroca Basin (Azanza et al. 1993; Casanovas-Vilar et al.

474 2011a, b, c), but they belong to different sedimentary basins (the Vallès-Penedès and
475 the Calatayud-Teruel basins, respectively).

476 One of the most striking morphological characters of *Iberictis* and other gulonines
477 (e.g., *Dehmictis*, *Plesiogulo*) is the distolingual expansion of the M1, which is also
478 present in some Neogene lutrines such as *Siamogale thailandica* Ginsburg et al., 1983,
479 *Paralutra jaegeri* and *Larctetictis dubia*, as well as melines such as *Parataxidea*
480 Zdansky, 1924, and *Melodon* Zdansky, 1924 (Ginsburg and Morales 1992, 2000; Grohé
481 et al. 2010). Although the dentition of *Iberictis* is very different from that of these early-
482 middle Miocene lutrines, isolated M1 of *Iberictis* could be easily mistaken for those of
483 the lutrines *Paralutra jaegeri* (also present at Pellecahus) and *Larctetictis dubia* (Fig.
484 6F–I). However, the M1 of these lutrines is less mesiodistally constricted, displays a
485 smaller styelar area, and a more developed paracone with a stouter cingulum, and it
486 further retains the hypocone.

487 A worn m1 BSPG Nr 645 (Fig. 6J1–3) from the early middle Miocene of Paşalar
488 (MN5, Turkey) was described and assigned to *Plesiogulo* sp. by Schmidt-Kittler (1976).
489 However, this designation is questionable in terms of morphology and age, with BSPG
490 Nr 645 being much older than other remains of *Plesiogulo* spp., which range from the
491 late Miocene to the early Pliocene (MN10–MN14). Furthermore, the Turkish mustelid
492 does not match with the morphology of *Plesiogulo*, with the former possessing a much
493 more developed m1 metaconid, a protoconid much higher than the paraconid, a
494 relatively longer talonid with a longer hypoconulid, and a deeper valley. Due to the
495 scarcity of the material and the above-mentioned morphological differences, we
496 consider that the m1 from Paşalar should be excluded from *Plesiogulo*. Although
497 BSPG Nr 645 shows some similarities with the m1 of *Iberictis*, the former specimen is
498 more robust, possesses a more developed metaconid, and displays a different talonid

499 morphology (longer talonid, non-beveled lingual wall of the hypoconid, deeper talonid
500 valley, higher entocristid, and lower hypoconid). These features indicate that an
501 assignment to *Iberictis* can be also discounted for the indeterminate Turkish specimen,
502 while its assignment is feasible within the subfamily Guloninae.

503

504 **Evolutionary History**

505 *Phylogenetic Relationships of the Guloninae, Mellivorinae, and Mustelinae*

506 During the Miocene, large terrestrial mustelids exhibited a wide taxonomic diversity in
507 Eurasia, Africa, and North America, being represented by genera such as *Dehmictis*,
508 *Ekorus*, *Eomellivora*, *Hoplictis*, *Iberictis*, *Ischyriictis*, and *Plesiogulo* (Zdansky 1924;
509 Teilhard 1945; Baskin 1998; Ginsburg 1999; Werdelin and Peigné 2010; Fig. 9).

510 Historically, these mustelids have been assigned to the extant subfamilies Guloninae,
511 Mellivorinae (honey badger), and Mustelinae (including weasels, polecats, minks, and
512 relatives; Baskin 1998; Ginsburg 1999; Werdelin and Peigné 2010). However, the
513 phylogenetic relationships among these genera and relative to extant mustelids

514 remained elusive (e.g., Ginsburg and Morales 1992; Baskin 1998; Ginsburg 1999;

515 Werdelin and Peigné 2010). Our cladistic analysis helps to unravel the relationship

516 between these extinct and extant taxa (Fig. 5), by showing that the genera *Dehmictis*,

517 *Iberictis*, *Ischyriictis*, and *Plesiogulo* belong to the Guloninae clade. The systematics of

518 these extinct mustelids has been controversial (e.g., Pia 1939; Webb 1969; Ginsburg

519 1977; Ginsburg and Morales 1992; McKenna and Bell 1997; Baskin 1998; Ginsburg

520 1999), not only due to the scarce and fragmentary craniodental remains available for

521 many extinct genera, but also to the presence of a mixture of primitive and derived

522 characters (Valenciano et al. 2017). Valenciano et al. (2017) performed a cladistic

523 analysis of some living and extinct large gulonines and mellivorines, and concluded that

524 the beech marten (*Martes foina*) and the fisher (*Pekania pennanti*), together with *Gulo*,
525 *Plesiogulo*, and the ischyrictin *Ischyrictis zibethoides* may be considered gulonines. The
526 inclusion of additional Miocene taxa in the present study further supports the distinction
527 of two subclades within the Guloninae, which we distinguish at the tribe rank: the
528 Gulonini (*Iberictis*, *Plesiogulo*, and *Gulo*) and the Ischyrictini (*Dehmictis* and
529 *Ischyrictis*). These family-group taxa were originally erected as “sub-subfamilies” by
530 Pia (1939), with the Ischyrictini including the extinct large mustelids *Ischyrictis*,
531 *Laphictis*, and *Hadriictis* (within subfamily Mellivorinae), and the Gulonini including
532 *Gulo* and *Plesiogulo* (within the Mustelinae). Subsequently, the Ischyrictini and the
533 Gulonini were considered at the tribe rank by Tobien (1955) and Webb (1969),
534 respectively. Different authors (Pia 1939; Tobien 1955; Webb 1969; Ginsburg 1977,
535 1999) have included these tribes into the Mellivorinae and the Guloninae, comprising
536 the genera *Eomellivora* (= *Hadriictis*), *Hopliictis*, *Iberictis*, *Gulo*, *Ischyrictis* (= *Laphictis*),
537 *Mellalictis*, *Mellivora*, and *Plesiogulo*.

538 Based on the results of the cladistic analysis reported in this paper, the Guloninae
539 clade (Figs. 5 and 9, Table 3) is defined, by the following synapomorphies: (1) I3
540 spreaded out laterally in relation to the I1-I2; (2) presence of a slender buccolingual
541 crista in the M1 from the paracone to the protocone (1 and 2 unambiguous
542 synapomorphies); and (3) relatively enlarged M1 lingual area (ambiguous
543 synapomorphy). The Guloninae also are characterized by the following traits: (1) P2
544 with a robust cingulum, absence of distal accessory cuspid in P3; (2) stout P4 cingular
545 parastyle; and (3) a relatively reduced p2. The subclade of *Dehmictis*+*Ischyrictis* is
546 distinguished here as a tribe (Ischyrictini) of more basal Guloninae, depicted by a more
547 primitive dentition (e.g., slender premolars) and with a relatively enlarged m1 talonid
548 (excluding *Izchyrictis zibethides*). The closer phylogenetic relationships between

549 *Iberictis*, *Plesiogulo*, and *Gulo* are reflected in the strict tree obtained (Figs. 5 and 9), in
550 which these genera conform the monophyletic tribe Gulonini (the total clade of
551 wolverines), characterized by the possession of wrinkled enamel and a robust premolar
552 morphology (Fig. 10). In particular, the Gulonini are defined (Table 3) by the following
553 unambiguous synapomorphies: (1) P3 with a stout cingulum and a distinct buccal
554 concavity; (2) P4 with both a strong buccal concavity and a stout cingulum surrounding
555 the whole tooth; (3) p2-p4 with strong cingula; absence of mesial and distal accessory
556 cuspids, with the exception of the p4, whose distal accessory cuspid is vestigial or
557 absent—some specimens of *Plesiogulo* not analyzed herein from the Turolian of Russia
558 ascribed to *Plesiogulo* cf. *P. brachygnathus* and *Plesiogulo* ex gr. *P. minor* possess a
559 small distal accessory cuspid in the p4; see Sotnikova (1995)— and thickening on the
560 mesial and distal cristids; and (4) m1 hypoconulid reduced or absent. It is also defined
561 by the following ambiguous synapomorphies: (1) P4 protocone distally displaced; and
562 (2) m1 metaconid individualized with a moderate size in the older taxa (*Iberictis* and
563 *Plesiogulo*), and lost in the living genera *Gulo*. The members of the clade
564 *Iberictis*+*Plesiogulo* (Figs. 5, 9 and 10) share more derived characters towards a *Canis*-
565 like dentition, with a prominent crushing area in the upper and lower molars. In
566 addition, they are characterized by the possession of an enlarged M1 in relation to the
567 P4, and a mesiodistal enlargement of the M1 lingual platform, which possesses a
568 concavity on the lingual edge. The late Miocene species of *Plesiogulo* are large to giant-
569 sized mustelids, characterized by a more robust dentition than in *Iberictis* and the
570 possession of other more derived traits (e.g., shorter lower premolars, trend to enlarge
571 the m1 talonid, by the presence of a crestiform m1 hypoconid, and a hypoconulid, as
572 well as a derived m2 that has lost the hypoconid).

573 Historically, it was accepted that the oldest known species of the extant genus

574 *Gulo* was *Gulo minor* Sotnikova, 1982, originally described based on a hemimandible
575 from the Lower Adycha River Basin (Arctic Siberia, Russia). These deposits were
576 initially interpreted as Pliocene in age (Sotnikova 1982), but later reinterpreted as late
577 middle Pleistocene (Sher et al. 2011). Subsequently, *G. minor* has been reported, based
578 on mandibular remains, from Udunga (Transbaikal region of Siberia, Russia), dated
579 between 3.1 and 3.6 Ma (MN15–MN16; Sotnikova 2008, 2010; Wolsan and Sotnikova
580 2013), thereby confirming an early late Pliocene age for this species (Fig. 9). Its lower
581 dentition is clearly wolverine-like, being characterized by small size, elongated
582 premolars without accessory cuspids, and an m1 similar in morphology to that of *Gulo*
583 *gulo*. A more primitive species ascribed into the genus has recently been described from
584 the early Blancan (early Pliocene, 4.9–4.5 Ma) of the Gray Fossil Site (Tennessee,
585 USA). *Gulo sudorus* Samuels et al., 2018, is represented by a left maxillary fragment
586 with the P2 and P4. This new wolverine represents the first datum of *Gulo*, being more
587 than one million year older than *G. minor*. Its dentition is intermediate between fisher
588 (*Pekania*) and later *Gulo* spp., suggesting that could represent an intermediate taxon,
589 which could have evolved in North America and later dispersed to Eurasia (Samuels et
590 al. 2018). Thus *Gulo sudorus* fills a gap in the origin of the genus, emerging as a
591 potential candidate to be the oldest member of *Gulo*, but the scarcity of its currently
592 available fossil remains precludes confirming such a hypothesis. More recently, in the
593 Pleistocene, *Gulo schlosseri* constitutes a better-known species from the early and
594 middle Pleistocene of Eurasia (Kormos 1914; Bonifay 1971; Xiaofeng and Haipo 1987;
595 Sotnikova 2010). It is also smaller and displays a less derived dentition than the living
596 wolverine. *Gulo schlosseri* and *Gulo gulo* have a very robust P4 and m1 trigonid, and
597 share derived characters towards a hypercarnivorous dentition, with a reduction in the
598 expansion of the P4 protocone, the M1 talon, the m1 talonid, and the m2. In both

599 species, the lower carnassial has lost the metaconid; the paraconid and protoconid are
600 equal in height, and the talonid has been reduced (in height, length, and width),
601 resembling a feloid-like tooth, in comparison with that of other mustelids. As discussed
602 above, our phylogenetic results set back the origin of a total wolverine clade to the early
603 Miocene, when *Iberictis* is recorded. This further indicates the existence of a ghost
604 lineage in the wolverine lineage of at least 12 Myr (from MN4 to MN15), and that the
605 genus *Gulo* (including *G. sudorus*, *G. minor*, *G. schlosseri*, and *G. gulo*) would have
606 not derived from any of the *Plesiogulo* species included in our analysis (Fig. 9).

607 Our cladistic results also indicate that the giant mustelids *Eomellivora piveteaui*
608 and *Ekorus ekakeran* are mellivorines, in agreement with Valenciano et al. (2015, 2017;
609 Fig. 5). *Eomellivora piveteaui*, *Ekorus ekakeran*, and the living *Mellivora capensis*
610 share among other synapomorphies the tendency of the posterior lacerate and jugular
611 foramina to possess separate openings, being the jugular foramen in a distolateral
612 position in relation to the posterior lacerate foramen, as well as a robust P3 with a distal
613 accessory cusp and a robust cingulum; a high m1 paraconid with a similar height to the
614 m1 protoconid and a reduced m2, which is lost in the single living representative of the
615 subfamily (Table 3). The living European polecat (*Mustela putorius*), which belongs to
616 the subfamily Mustelinae, is nested in our analysis as the sister taxon of the clade
617 composed of the three above mentioned species, but the node is only very weakly
618 supported. Molecular phylogenetic analyses support mustelines as the sister group of
619 lutrines (otters; e.g., Koepfli et al. 2008; Sato et al. 2012) instead of mellivorines,
620 although it should be taken into account that the phylogenetic placement of *Mellivora*
621 *capensis* (the only living mellivorine) is contentious (Sato et al. 2012), being generally
622 considered to occupy a basal position within the Mustelidae (Koepfli et al. 2008; Sato et
623 al. 2012). The primitive and hypercarnivorous *Hoplictis noueli* from Artenay (France,

624 MN4), only known by mandibles and an isolated M1 (Mayet 1908; Helbing 1930;
625 Ginsburg 1961), is recovered by our analysis as the basalmost taxon of the mellivorine
626 clade (Fig. 9). However, the fact that it occupies a more basal position than *Mustela*
627 *putorius*, even if this placement is weakly supported, does not allow us to conclusively
628 discount the possibility that *Hoplictis* precedes the divergence between mellivorines and
629 mustelines. The discovery of additional remains of the upper dentition of *Hoplictis*
630 *noueli* might therefore contribute to clarify further the phylogenetic relationships
631 between this basal form and other investigated taxa, thereby helping to decipher the
632 relationships between the Mellivorinae and the Mustelinae.

633

634 *Remarks on the Diet of the Gulonini*

635 Both *Iberictis* and the more derived *Plesiogulo* are characterized by a robust
636 dentition with a relatively long m1 as well as long and stout M1 and P4 (Fig. 10). These
637 traits are useful for opportunistic foraging and also for crushing bones, as is the case
638 among extant canids (Sillero-Zubiri 2009). This set of traits together with the possession of
639 a mesiodistal enlargement of the M1 lingual platform, and the presence of a concavity
640 on the lingual edge are also present in some lineages of Euroasiatic Miocene lutrines
641 such as *Paralutra jaegeri*, *Lartetictis dubia*, and *Siamogale thailandica*, which have
642 been interpreted recently as badger-like otters (Wang et al. 2017) because their dentition
643 is adapted for crushing food. Thus, the interpretation of these features found in these
644 gulonines, lutrines, and also in melines as a convergence due to a dietary shift toward a
645 more omnivorous or durophagous diet is reasonable. The characteristic shortening of
646 the M1 talon and m1 talonid of *Gulo*, together with other craniodental features
647 (thickening of the m1 trigonid and shortening of the muzzle), represent an alternative
648 adaptation for crushing bones with the premolars and, especially, with the carnassials

649 (Fig. 10). The diet of *Gulo gulo* includes the carcasses of large ungulates such as moose
650 and reinder, as well as preying opportunistically on deer, sheep, and small vertebrates
651 (Larivière and Jennings 2009). The shortening of the muzzle enabled the production of
652 higher bite forces, thereby improving the efficiency for crushing bones, which constitute
653 an important portion of the diet of this taxon (Larivière and Jennings 2009). Preliminary
654 studies of the masticatory apparatus of large and giant mustelids suggested that *Gulo*
655 *gulo* is able to produce relatively greater bite forces than *Plesiogulo crassa* (Valenciano
656 et al. 2016b), although the estimates obtained for both taxa were quite high for a
657 carnivoran of their size. Morphological similarities in the dentition of *Plesiogulo* and
658 *Gulo*, such as the size and stoutness of the premolar series, suggest that *Plesiogulo* was
659 similarly an opportunistic feeder able to process bone rather efficiently (Harrison 1981).
660 The latter specialization is less evident in *Iberictis*, which might have been a more
661 opportunistic feeder than *Plesiogulo* and *Gulo*. However, both the shape of the teeth and
662 the horizontal wear pattern displayed by some specimens (e.g., Figs. 2A, B, E, 4A and
663 6E) support the consumption of hard food items such as bones (as in living jackals;
664 Sillero-Zubiri 2009).

665

666 **Summary and Conclusions**

667

668 Based on previously unpublished remains from the early Miocene (MN4) of els Casots
669 (Vallès-Penedès Basin), the extinct gulonine mustelid *I. buloti* is reported for the first
670 time from the Iberian Peninsula, where only its sister species, *I. azanzae*, was
671 previously known. The new material of both species described here fills an important
672 gap in the knowledge of these mustelids and confirms the taxonomic validity of both
673 species. The sample of *I. buloti* from els Casots includes more abundant material than

674 that from the type locality (MN4 of Pellecahus, France), and therefore it enlarges the
675 knowledge of this genus in relation to the wolverine lineage. A cladistic analysis of
676 extinct and extant gulonines, mustelines, and mellivorines indicates that the wolverine
677 lineage is much older than previously thought. In particular, *Iberictis* emerges as the
678 oldest member of the Gulonini (the total clade of wolverines, currently represented only
679 by the living *Gulo gulo*), thus allowing to track the fossil record of this clade back to the
680 early Miocene (16.5–16.3 Ma). *Iberictis* is further nested as the sister group of the large
681 late Miocene gulonine *Plesiogulo*, thereby indicating that none of the analyzed species
682 of the latter genus is a likely direct ancestor of *Gulo*. The results of our phylogenetic
683 analysis further allows us to rearrange the analyzed large Miocene genera into two
684 distinct mustelid subfamilies: *Dehmictis* and *Ischyriactis* (Ischyriactini), together with the
685 aforementioned genera *Iberictis* and *Plesiogulo* (Gulonini) are classified as gulonines;
686 whereas *Ekorus*, *Eomellivora*, and *Hoplictis* are classified as mellivorines, being
687 possibly more closely related to the Mustelinae (represented here by *Mustela*).

688

689 **Acknowledgments** We would like to thank the following curators and collection
690 managers for access to comparative material under their care: E. Westwig and J.
691 Galking (AMNH), D. Kalthoff (NRM), A. Prieur (FSL), C. Argot (MNHN), J.O.R.
692 Ebbestad and V. Berg-Madsen (PMU), D. Lunde (USNM), U.B. Göhlich (NHMW), J.I.
693 Canudo (MPZ), and E. López Errasquin and S. Fraile (MNCN). We are grateful to L.
694 Werdelin (NRM) for kindly allowing us to study the cast of the skull and mandibles of
695 *Ekorus ekakeran*. We further thank M. March and J. Galindo for assistance with the ICP
696 collections; G. Rössner (BSPG) for the pictures of *Plesiogulo* sp. from Paşalar
697 (Turkey); S. Mayda (Ege University, Turkey) for the pictures of *Paralutra jaegeri* from
698 Ravensburg and Steinheim (Germany), *Ischyriactis mustelinus* from La Grive-Saint-

699 Alban (France) and Erkertshofen 2 (Germany), and *Dehmictis vorax* from Wintershof-
700 West (Germany); B. Azanza (Universidad de Zaragoza) for the pictures of old material
701 of *I. azanzae*; J.I. Canudo (MPZ) for cataloguing the new material of *I. azanzae*; S.
702 Peigné (MNHN) and the photographer Philippe Loubry (UMR7207, MNHN) for the
703 pictures of *I. buloti* from Pellecahus (France); S. Govender and R. Govender (SAM) for
704 the pictures of *Plesiogulo monspessulanus* from Langebaanweg; and L. Costeur (NMB)
705 for the pictures of *Hoplictis noueli* from Artenay (France). We also are grateful to M.
706 Sotnikova (Geological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russia) for
707 her help concerning *Gulo minor*, and to M. Pina (ICP) for assistance with the pictures of
708 *I. buloti* from els Casots. A.V. was researcher in formation in the CSIC program JAE-
709 PRE_CP2011 (CSIC program “Junta para la ampliación de estudios”), co-funded by the
710 European Social Fund. This research received support by A.V. from the SYNTHESYS3
711 Project <http://www.synthesys.info/> (SYNTHESYS; AT-TAF-5457), which is financed
712 by European Community Research Infrastructure Action under the FP7 “Capacities”
713 Programme, and the European Union’s Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-
714 2013) under grant agreement n° 226506 (SYNTHESYS; SE-TAF-3637). A.V. also
715 received support by an American Museum of Natural History Collection Study Grant
716 Program 2014. The support of the DST-NFR Centre of Excellence in Palaeosciences
717 (CoE-Pal) toward this research for A. V. (COE2018-09POST) is hereby acknowledged.
718 Opinions expressed and conclusions arrived at, are those of the author and are not
719 necessarily to be attributed to the CoE. This study was also supported by CGL2015-
720 68333-P (MINECO/FEDER-UE), Agencia Estatal de Investigación–European Regional
721 Development Fund of the European Union (CGL2016-76431-P, AEI/FEDER, EU), the
722 Generalitat de Catalunya (CERCA Programme), and the research group UCM 910607.
723 We are also indebted to the Editor-in-Chief J.R. Wible, and both J. Baskin and one

724 anonymous reviewer for their useful comments and suggestions, which significantly
725 improved the original manuscript. We want to express our deepest gratitude to the late
726 Stéphane Peigné (MNHN), a colleague, friend and a recognized world expert in
727 Neogene carnivorans, who passed away during the development of this project.

728

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1024

1025 **Figure captions**

1026

1027 **Fig. 1.** Schematic geological map of the Vallès-Penedès Basin, showing the main
 1028 geological units as well as the situation of els Casots. Modified from Alba et al. (2014).

1029 **Fig. 2.** New dental remains of *Iberictis azanzae*, from Artesilla. **A.** MPZ-2018/42, left
 1030 P4 protocone. **A.1.** Distal view, **A.2.** Lingual view, **A.3.** Buccal view, **A.4.** Occlusal
 1031 view; **B.** MPZ-2018/43, right fragment of M1, occlusal view; **C.** MPZ-2018/39, left c,
 1032 **C.1.** Buccal view, **C.2.** Lingual view, **C.3.** Distal view; **D.** MPZ-2018/40, left c, **D.1.**
 1033 Buccal view, **D.2.** Lingual view, **D.3.** Distal view; **E.** MPZ-2018/41, left p4, **E.1.**
 1034 Buccal view, **E.2.** Lingual view, **E.3.** Occlusal view.

1035 **Fig. 3.** Upper dentition of *Iberictis buloti* from els Casots. **A.** IPS10076, right maxillary
 1036 fragment with I3, C, P2–P4, M1, buccal view; **B.** IPS10085, right C. **B.1.** Buccal view,
 1037 **B.2.** Distal view, **B.3.** Lingual view; **C.** IPS24159, right C, buccal view; **D.** IPS10083,
 1038 right maxillary fragment with P2–P4, **D.1.** Buccal view, **D.2.** Occlusal view, **D.3.**
 1039 Lingual view; **E.** IPS24701, right maxillary fragment with P2–P3 roots and P4–M1
 1040 (partially broken), **E.1.** Buccal view, **E.2.** Occlusal view; **F.** IPS24701, left maxillary
 1041 fragment with partial root of P3, a complete P4 and a lingual part of the M1, **F.1.** Buccal
 1042 view, **F.2.** Occlusal view; **G.** IPS100599, left maxillary fragment with complete P3 and

1043 broken P4. **G.1.** Buccal view, **G.2.** Occlusal view, **G.3.** Lingual view; **H.** IPS36425, left
1044 P3. **H.1.** Buccal view, **H.2.** Occlusal view, **H.3.** Lingual view; **I.** IPS36425, left P4. **I.1.**
1045 Buccal view, **I.2.** Occlusal view, **I.3.** Mesial view; **J.** IPS10072 left M1, Occlusal view;
1046 **K.** IPS36425, partial left M1, occlusal view; **L.** IPS105255, partial left M1, occlusal
1047 view; **M.** IPS10077, left maxillary fragment with P4–M1, Occlusal view.

1048 **Fig. 4.** Lower dentition of *Iberictis buloti* from els Casots. **A.** IPS10067, right
1049 hemimandible with c, p2–m1, **A.1.** Buccal view, **A.2.** Lingual view, **A.3.** Oclussal view;
1050 **B.** IPS10069, left hemimandible with p4–m1, **B.1.** Buccal view, **B.2.** Lingual view, **B.3.**
1051 Oclussal view; **C.** IPS10066, left hemimandible with c, p2–m2, **C.1.** Buccal view, **C.2.**
1052 Lingual view, **C. 3.** Oclussal view; **D.** IPS10079, right hemimandible with p3–p4 and
1053 m1, **D.1.** Buccal view, **D.2.** Lingual view, **D.3.** Oclussal view; **E.** IPS24700, right
1054 hemimandible with p2–p4 and m1, **E.1.** Lingual view, **E.2.** Occlusal view; **F.** IPS10084
1055 right hemimandible with p2–p4 and m1, buccal view; **G.** IPS105256, left p4, **G.1.**
1056 Buccal view, **G.2.** Lingual view, **G.3.** Oclussal view; **H.** IPS24700, left mandibular
1057 fragment with m1 talonid and m2, **H.1.** Buccal view, **H.2.** Lingual view, **H.3.** Oclusal
1058 view; **I.** IPS10088, m2. **I.1.** Buccal view, **I.2.** Occlusal view.

1059 **Fig. 5.** Results of the cladistic analysis performed in this paper to decipher the
1060 phylogenetic relationship of *Iberictis buloti* (P = Pellecahus, C = els Casots) with
1061 selected extinct large Neogene mustelids and living musteloids. The cladogram depicts
1062 the strict consensus of the three most parsimonious trees (see main text for further
1063 details). Numbers below nodes are Bremer indices, and numbers above nodes are
1064 Bootstrap support percentages (only shown when ≥ 50). Apomorphies for each node are
1065 reported in Table 3.

1066 **Fig. 6.** The dentition of *Iberictis* compared with that of other early and middle Miocene
1067 mustelids. **A.** Composed maxillary specimen of *Iberictis azanzae* from Artesilla,

1068 comprised by MPZ-16522 (holotype, left maxillary fragment with P4 and partial M1)
1069 and by MPZ-2018/43 (buccal part of a right M1, mirrored specimen for comparison),
1070 occlusal view; **B.** MNHN LRM 782 and MNHN LRM 789, paratypes of *Iberictis buloti*
1071 from Pellecahus (composed specimen), left maxillary fragment with P3–P4 (MNHN
1072 LRM 782), and left M1 fragment (MNHN LRM 789); **C.** IPS10077, *Iberictis buloti*
1073 from els Casots, left maxillary fragment with P4–M1, occlusal view; **D.** IPS10072,
1074 *Iberictis buloti* from els Casots, left M1, occlusal view; **E.** MNHN LRM 1044, holotype
1075 of *Iberictis buloti* from Pellecahus, right hemimandible with p3–m1, **E.1.** Buccal view,
1076 **E.2.** Lingual view, **E.3.** Occlusal view; **F.** SMNS 4082, left maxillary with P2–P4 of
1077 *Paralutra jaegeri* from Steinheim (see also Helbing, 1936: Fig. 1), occlusal view; **G.**
1078 SMNS 16816, left M1 of *Paralutra jaegeri* from Steinheim (see also Helbing, 1936:
1079 Fig. 2), occlusal view; **H.** SMNS T.D. 537, left M1 of *Paralutra jaegeri* from
1080 Ravensburg, described initially by Helbing (1928) as cf. *Lutra lorteti* (see also Helbing,
1081 1928: Fig. 3), and subsequently synonymized by him (Helbing, 1936) with *Pa. jaegeri*,
1082 occlusal view; **I.** MNHN Sa 843, left M1 of *Lartetictis dubia* from Sansan, occlusal
1083 view; **J.** BSPG Nr 645 right m1 of Guloninae indet. described as *Plesiogulo* sp. by
1084 Schmidt-Kittler (1976) from Paşalar, **J.1.** Buccal view, **J.2.** Lingual view, **J.3.** Occlusal
1085 view.

1086 **Fig. 7.** Measurements (mm) of the upper dentition of *Iberictis* spp., *Gulo gulo* and
1087 *Mellivora capensis*, as depicted by bivariate plots of buccolingual width (W) vs.
1088 mesiodistal length (L). **A.** C; **B.** P2; **C.** P3; **D.** P4, **E.** M1.

1089 **Fig. 8.** Measurements (mm) of the lower dentition of *Iberictis* spp., Guloninae indet.
1090 from Paşalar, *Gulo gulo* and *Mellivora capensis*, as depicted by bivariate plots of
1091 buccolingual width (W) vs. mesiodistal length (L). **A.** c; **B.** p2; **C.** p3; **D.** p4, **E.** m1; **F.**
1092 m2.

1093 **Fig. 9.** Calibrated phylogenetic hypothesis based on our cladistic analysis.
1094 Chronostratigraphical and biochronological correlations of North American land
1095 mammal age (NALMA) based on a Tedford et al. (2004), Albright et al. (2008) and
1096 Hilgen et al. (2012); European Mammal Neogene Units (MN) based on Hilgen et al.
1097 (2012) and Morales et al. (2013). Stratigraphic ranges of the taxa based on Kormos
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1100 (1989), Ginsburg and Morales (1992), Alcalá et al. (1994), Sotnikova (1995, 2008),
1101 Ginsburg (1999), Werdelin (2003), Montoya et al. (2011), Sher et al. (2011), Peigné
1102 (2012), Wolsan and Sotnikova (2013), and Valenciano et al. (2015). *Gulo sudorus* and
1103 *G. minor* are placed here based on Sotnikova (1982, 2010) and Samuels et al. (2018),
1104 although they were not included in our cladistics analysis.

1105 **Fig. 10.** The dentition of *Iberictis* compared with that of other members of the
1106 wolverine total clade. **A.** Fragment of the cranium IPS10076 of *Iberictis buloti* from els
1107 Casots with its mandible IPS10067, lateral view; **B.** IPS24701, partial maxilla of the
1108 same specimen of *Iberictis buloti* from els Casots, occlusal view; **C.** IPS10077 *Iberictis*
1109 *buloti* from els Casots, left maxillary fragment with P4–M1, occlusal view; **D.** PMU
1110 M3805, cranium of *Plesiogulo crassa* from Locality 108, China (specimen Ex. 8 of
1111 Zdansky, 1924), occlusal view; **E.** *Gulo gulo* cranium occlusal view; **F.** IPS10067,
1112 *Iberictis buloti* from els Casots, right hemimandible with c, p2–m1, mirrored specimen
1113 for comparison, **F.1.** Occlusal view, **F.2.** Buccal view; **G.** PMU M3806, mandible of
1114 *Plesiogulo crassa* from Locality 108, China (specimen Ex. 8 of Zdansky, 1924; same
1115 individual as PMU M3805), **G.1.** Occlusal view, **G.2.** Buccal view; **H.** *Gulo gulo*,
1116 mandible (same individual as depicted in E), **H.1.** occlusal view, **H.2.** buccal view.
1117

1118 **Table captions**

1119 **Table 1.** Upper teeth measurements (in mm) of mesiodistal length (L) and buccolingual
1120 width (W) of *Iberictis buloti* from els Casots (C) and Pellecahus (P), and *Iberictis*
1121 *azanzae* from Artesilla (A). Estimated values are reported within parentheses.
1122 **Table 2.** Lower teeth measurements (in mm) of mesiodistal length (L) and buccolingual
1123 width (W) of *Iberictis buloti* from els Casots (C) and Pellecahus (P), and *Iberictis*
1124 *azanzae* from Artesilla (A). Estimated values are reported within parentheses.
1125 **Table 3.** Synapomorphies for selected nodes (see Fig. 5), as indicated by character
1126 numbers followed by character states within parentheses. Italics denote ambiguous
1127 synapomorphies.

1128

1129 **Appendices captions**

1130

1131 **Appendix 1.** Descriptions of dental characters used in the phylogenetic analysis
1132 performed in this work.
1133 **Appendix 2.** Character-taxon matrix used in the phylogenetic analysis performed in this
1134 work.
1135 **Appendix 3.** Character-taxon matrix in nexus format.

1136

PRE-NEOGENE SUBSTRATE

- Paleozoic to Mesozoic
- Paleogene

NEOGENE MARINE UNITS

- Late Burdigalian-Langhian
- Langhian (coralgal carbonate platform)
- Serravallian

CONTINENTAL NEOGENE UNITS

- Early Miocene
- Middle Miocene-Pleistocene

- Main normal faults
- Cities and towns
- Paleontological sites

Mephitis mephitis

Bassariscus astutus

Iberictis buloti (P)

Iberictis buloti (C)

Iberictis azanzae

Plesiogulo monspessulanus

Plesiogulo crassa

Plesiogulo marshalli

Plesiogulo lindsayi

Gulo gulo

Gulo schlosseri

Dehmictis vorax

Ischyriictis zibethoides

Ischyriictis mustelinus

Mellivora capensis

Ekorus ekakeran

Eomellivora piveteaui

Mustela putorius

Hoplictis noueli

OUTGROUP

GULONINI

GULONINAE

ISCHYRICCTINI

MELLIVORINAE

MUSTELINAE

MUSTELOIDEA

△ *Iberictis buloti* (Pellecahus)
 ● *Iberictis buloti* (els Casots)
 □ *Iberictis azanzae* (Artesilla)
 ● *Gulo gulo*
 ○ *Mellivora capensis*

2 cm

Species	Locality	Catalog No.	C		P2		P3		P4		M1	
			L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10085	9.5	6.5								
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10086	9.6	6.6								
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS24159	9.9	6.8								
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10076			6.2	2.8	8.2	4.5	12	8.6	8.6	10.7
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10083			6.7	3.5	8.8	4.9	13.3	9.2		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10077							12.5	8	9	11.9
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS85598							13.6	9.4		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10072									8.8	13.5
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS105255									10	
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS100599					9.2	5.3	(13.6)	10.2		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS36425						5.2	14.1	10.6	9	
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS24701 left							13.4	9.4	8.29	
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS24701 right			(6.9)	(3.7)	(8.6)	(4.6)	13.6	9.2	(7.7)	12.9
<i>I. buloti</i>	P	MNCN-74707					7.89	5.62	14.25	10.5		
<i>I. buloti</i>	P	MNHN LRM782							13	8.8		
<i>I. buloti</i>	P	MNHN LRM 789									9.6	(13.4)
<i>I. azanzae</i>	A	MPZ-16522							16	10.5	10.5	(16.0)

Species	Locality	Catalog No.	c		p2		p3		p4		m1		m2	
			L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W	L	W
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS24107							10.7	5.4			6.4	5.1
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS24700 left					7.5	4.2	10.3	5.2				
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS24700 right	9.7	7.1	6.1	3.4	7.4	4	9.5	5	15.9	6		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS85595							9.6	4.8	14.79	4.8*		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10084			6.1	3.3	8.1	4.2	10.5	5	14.92	6.1		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10069							9.8	5.2	15.49	5.9		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS24686							9.8	4.9	14.32	6		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10080			6.1	3.4	8.4	4.1	10.7	5.5				
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10079					8.4	4.3	11.1	5.5	16.42	6.1		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10066	9.3	5.6	6.9	3.3	7.3	4.2	10.1	5.1	14.32	(5.4)	5.4	4.7
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10067	8.2	6.1	6.1	3.2	7.2	4.2	9.9	5.2	14.12	5.9		
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS10068	7.9	5.2			7.3	4						
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS 10088											7.1	5.6
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS 10070					7.3	3.8	(9.2)	(5.2)				
<i>I. buloti</i>	C	IPS 105256							10.7	5.6				
<i>I. buloti</i>	P	MNHN LRM1044					7.5	4.1	10.2	5.1	14.7	6.2		
<i>I. buloti</i>	P	MNHN LRM1032							10.2	5.3	15.3	6.1		
<i>I. azanzae</i>	A	MPZ-2018/39	9.0	6.0										
<i>I. azanzae</i>	A	MPZ-2018/40	8.3	6.8										
<i>I. azanzae</i>	A	MPZ-2018/41							(9.9)	5.0				
<i>I. azanzae</i>	A	MPZ-16525	9	5.8										
<i>I. azanzae</i>	A	MPZ-16523							9.6	4.7				
<i>I. azanzae</i>	A	MPZ-16524									16	6.2		
<i>I. azanzae</i>	A	MPZ-16526											6.7	5.3

Node	Character (state)
A	7 (0); 34 (1), 37 (1)
B	17 (1); 18 (1); 21 (1); 26 (1); 27 (1); 45 (1); 46 (1); 50 (1); 51 (1); 52 (1); 54 (1); 56 (1); 60 (0); 69 (0)
C	8 (0); 29 (1); 35 (1); 38 (1); 39 (1); 62 (0)
D	11 (0); 21 (0); 22 (1); 23 (1); 25 (1); 32 (0); 44 (0); 50 (0); 76 (0)
E	26 (0); 35 (0); 36 (0)
F	66 (1); 69 (1)
G	13 (1)
H	19 (0); 28 (2); 30 (0); 37 (0); 59 (1); 61 (1); 67 (2); 71 (2); 74 (1);
I	11 (0); 49 (0); 57 (0); 62 (2); 66 (1)
J	33 (1); 48 (0); 67 (2)
K	31 (1); 35 (1); 48 (0); 60 (1); 64 (1); 65 (1); 67 (1); 68 (1); 70 (2); 71 (2)
L	33 (1); 59 (1); 63 (1); 73 (1); 74 (1)
M	1 (1); 13 (1); 16 (0); 17 (1); 18 (1); 27 (1); 37 (1); 50 (1); 61 (1); 75 (1)
N	15 (1); 24 (2); 26 (1); 42 (1); 43 (1); 47 (1); 53 (1); 64 (0)